

A NOVEL POWER REDUCTION TECHNIQUE FOR DUAL-THRESHOLD DOMINO LOGIC IN SUB-65NM TECHNOLOGY

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ABSTRACT

A novel technique for dual- threshold is proposed and examined with inputs and clock signals combination in 65nm dual- threshold footerless domino circuit for reduced leakage current. In this technique a p-type and an n-type leakage controlled transistor (LCTs) are introduced between the pull-up and pull-down network and the gate of one is controlled by the source of the other. A high-threshold transistor is used in the input for reducing gate oxide leakage current which becomes dominant in nanometer technology. Simulations based on 65nm BISM4 model for proposed domino circuits shows that CLIL (clock low and input low) and CHIH (clock high and input high) state is ineffective for lowering leakage current. The CLIH (clock low input high) state is only effective to suppress the leakage at low and high temperatures for wide fan-in domino circuits but for AND gate CHIL (clock high input low) state is preferred to reduce the leakage current. The proposed circuit technique for AND2, OR2, OR4 and OR8 circuits reduces the active power consumption by 39.6% to 57.9% and by 32.4% to 40.3% at low and high die temperatures respectively when compared to the standard dual-threshold voltage domino logic circuits.

KEYWORDS

Dual-Threshold, Domino logic, Subthreshold leakage, Gate oxide tunneling, Leakage current.

1. INTRODUCTION

As a common logic in high-speed performance chip design, domino circuits are widely used and can be classified into footerless and footed domino [1-3]. The footed domino has better timing characteristics because the footer transistor isolates the pull-down network (PDN) from ground during precharge phase so the dynamic node does not discharge through the PDN. In footerless dominos circuit evaluation delay is reduced and consumes less power. Owing different characteristics the footerless and footed dominos both are extensively used in high microprocessors. In a multistage domino, the first stage is typically footed and the others in chain are footerless [3].

With aggressive scaling of CMOS device reduces the threshold voltage (V_t) accompanies with the exponential increase of subthreshold leakage current (I_{sub}) which is a concern not only for leakage power consumption but also for noise immunity. For solving I_{sub} problem many techniques at circuit level have been proposed which includes input vector control [4], body-bias control [5], dual- V_t [6], transistor-stack effect [7] and so on.

In fact, I_{gate} increases exponentially with the scaling of oxide thickness (t_{ox}). 2003 International Technology Roadmap for Semiconductor (ITRS) predicts that t_{ox} will decrease from 13Å for the 65nm generation to 9Å for 35nm [8]. With such thin t_{ox} , accordingly, I_{gate} is becoming a

significant contributor to the total leakage current as CMOS process advances to sub-65nm regime. The probability of electron tunneling is much higher than the probability of hole tunneling through the silicon- dioxide used as gate oxide in bulk CMOS technology. Simulation results shows that I_{gate} of a PMOS device is much lower when compared with I_{gate} of NMOS device as shown in Fig. 1 with similar physical dimensions (width, length and t_{ox}) in a 65 nm technology and at the same potential difference across the gate insulator. The I_{gate} produced by an NMOS transistor is 81.5 times higher at supply voltage 1.2V and 16 times higher at supply voltage of 0.2V when compared with PMOS transistor. The difference of I_{gate} between NMOS and PMOS transistor is increased with increase of supply voltage as illustrated in Fig. 1. During ideal mode or at low temperature most of the power consumption occurs due to I_{gate} and during non-ideal mode or at high temperature most of the power is consumed by the I_{sub} . So new circuit technique should be efficient enough to reduce the I_{gate} and I_{sub} at low and high temperatures respectively.

Figure 1. Comparison of gate oxide leakage current produced by a NMOS and PMOS transistors with same physical dimensions.

Kao et al. [6] indicated that high clock and high input (CHIH) signals are preferable to reduce I_{sub} in sleep mode dual- V_t footerless domino gate. However, the CHIH sleep state produces great gate oxide leakage current (I_{gate}) through the PDN transistors in both footed and footerless dominos. The most recent, comprehensive analysis of the total leakage at 65nm including I_{sub} and I_{gate} of footerless dominos was carried out by Z. Liu et al. [9]. Considering the impact of I_{gate} on the total leakage current, the study indicates that high clock and low input (CHIL) state is preferable in dual- V_t footerless dominos, particularly at low sleep temperatures.

In this paper, a new circuit technique is proposed which reduces the I_{gate} and I_{sub} leakage current with inputs and clock signal combination. The proposed circuit consumes less active power for low and high die temperatures but with more delay and area overhead compared with standard dual-threshold (dual- V_t) domino logic circuit.

The paper is organized as follows: Section 2 characterizes leakage current in domino circuit are surveyed. In Section 3 the proposed lector dual- V_t domino circuit is explained. Simulation results are given in Section 4 following the conclusion in Section 5.

2. CHARACTERISTICS OF LEAKAGE CURRENT IN DOMINO CIRCUIT

This section is divided into two subsections namely 2.1 and 2.2. In Section 2.1 comparison of sub threshold and gate oxide leakage current produced by PMOS and NMOS transistors for low- V_t and high- V_t is shown. In Section 2.2 working of standard dual- V_t domino is discussed.

2.1. I_{sub} and I_{gate} current analysis of a single transistor

Maximum gate oxide leakage and sub threshold leakage currents produced by PMOS and NMOS is shown in Fig. 2. In Fig. 2(a) four components of I_{gate} are shown: Gate to channel tunneling current (I_{gc}), gate-to-source tunneling current (I_{gs}), gate-to-drain tunneling current (I_{gd}) and gate-to-body tunneling current (I_{gb}) [9]. I_{gs} and I_{gd} are the edge tunneling currents from gate to source and drain terminals respectively, through the gate-to-source and gate-to-drain overlap areas. I_{gc} is shared between source and drain terminals [10]. I_{gb} is smaller than the other three components of gate tunneling current and it is typically several orders of magnitude.

Figure 2. State of maximum gate oxide and subthreshold leakage current, in NMOS and PMOS transistors. (a) Maximum gate oxide leakage current state. (b) Maximum subthreshold leakage current state.

As shown in Fig. 2(a) maximum gate oxide leakage current flows when the transistor is turned ON and maximum potential difference between gate-to-source and gate-to-drain terminals. As shown in Fig. 2(b) maximum sub threshold leakage current flows when the transistor is turned OFF and maximum the potential difference between source and drain terminals.

A comparison of normalized gate oxide and subthreshold leakage currents produced by NMOS and PMOS transistors for low- V_t and high- V_t in a 65nm dual- V_t CMOS technology is listed in Table 1. The data are measured for low and high die temperatures.

Table 1. Normalized gate oxide and subthreshold leakage currents for NMOS and PMOS (low- V_t and high- V_t) transistors at low and high die temperatures.

	NMOS Transistor		PMOS Transistor	
	Low- V_t	High- V_t	Low- V_t	High- V_t
I_{sub} (110°C)	1.53	1.98	1.16	1
I_{gate} (110°C)	.89	.098	.011	.0003
I_{sub} (25°C)	1.18	1.41	1.17	1
I_{gate} (25°C)	2.61	.29	.036	.0011

Transistor Length = 65nm, Width = 1 μ m, Low- V_t = 0.22V, High- V_t = 0.423V, V_{DD} = 1V. For each temperature, leakage currents are normalized by subthreshold leakage current produced by a high- V_t PMOS transistor.

Firstly, the I_{gate} produced by a low- V_t NMOS is 81x and 72.5x higher than the I_{gate} produced by a low- V_t PMOS at 110°C and 25°C respectively, as illustrated in Table 1. It shows that the probability of hole tunneling is much smaller than the probability of electron tunneling through

the gate insulator. Therefore, the I_{gate} produced by a PMOS device is much smaller than the I_{gate} produced by a NMOS device with similar physical dimensions (width, length and t_{ox}) in a 65 nm technology and at the same potential difference across the gate insulator [11].

Secondly, the I_{gate} produced by a low- V_t NMOS is 9.1x at 110°C and 9x at 25°C higher than I_{gate} by a high- V_t NMOS transistor. Relatively higher gate tunneling barrier for the electrons is exploited in this paper by using a high- V_t NMOS transistor at the input of a domino circuits to reduce the gate oxide leakage current overhead of the proposed dual- V_t domino circuit technique.

2.2. Standard Dual- V_t Domino Logic

The standard dual- V_t domino logic is shown in Fig.3. The first dual- V_t domino logic circuit was proposed by Kao [12] employing dual- V_t transistors for reduction of subthreshold leakage circuit. For maintaining the same delay as in standard footerless domino circuit the critical signal transition should occur through low- V_t during evaluation phase. Alternatively, during precharge phase signal transition is not a critical issue for maintaining in the performance of the circuit and the transistors that are active during precharge phase having high- V_t transistor [13]. The feedback keeper transistor parallel with precharge transistor whose gate is biased with the output voltage is employed to maintain the dynamic voltage against coupling noise, charge sharing problem and subthreshold leakage current [14].

The working of standard dual- V_t domino circuit is as follows: When the clock is low the precharge transistor MP_1 (high- V_t) is ON and charges the dynamic node, this phase is called precharge phase. During the precharge phase output node goes low and MP_2 (high- V_t) transistor turns ON maintaining the dynamic node in the high state. The output of the domino logic is independent of the inputs applied at the evaluation network only the leakage current is dependent on the input vectors applied. Now when the clock is high transistor, MP_1 is OFF and transistor MP_2 is dependent on the output of the domino circuit, this phase is called evaluation phase. The dynamic node charging will depend on the input vectors applied and according to that output node will be low or high. The subthreshold and gate oxide leakage will also depend on the applied input vectors.

Figure 3. Standard Dual- V_t Domino Logic OR Gate. High- V_t transistors are represented by thick line in channel region.

3. LECTOR DUAL - V_T DOMINO LOGIC

The proposed circuit technique effectively enhances the reduction of subthreshold and gate oxide leakage simultaneously. The proposed circuit is illustrated in Fig.4. The concept behind the approach is the reduction of leakage power using the effective stacking of transistor between the path from supply voltage to ground. The observation is based on [15], [16] and [17] in which a state with only one transistor is OFF between the supply voltage and ground is more leaky than the state with more than one transistor is off in a path from supply voltage to ground.

Figure 4. Proposed Lector Dual- V_t Domino Logic OR Gate. High- V_t transistors are represented by thick line in channel region.

In our approach a low- V_t MP_4 (PMOS) and MN_2 (NMOS) LCTs are introduced between the precharge and evaluation network and the gate of these transistors are controlled by the source of each other. The drain node of MP_4 and MN_2 are connected together to form the input of the inverter. In this configuration, transistor MP_4 and MN_2 switching will depend on the voltage potential at node N_2 and N_1 respectively. So for any combination of input in the pull-down network one of the LCT will operate near its cut-off region and increase the resistance between V_{DD} and ground rails leads to the reduction of leakage current. High- V_t NMOS transistors replaces the low- V_t input transistors of pull-down network to reduce the gate oxide leakage current.

The proposed domino gate operates similar to standard dual- V_t domino gate. In proposed domino circuit when the clock signal turns low the dynamic node is charged high through the transistor MP_1 (high- V_t) and MP_4 (low- V_t). The charging of dynamic node is almost independent of the previous clock input state. Suppose if the inputs are low before the clock sets low then node N_2 will be at low potential and transistor MP_4 offers the less resistance path for charging of dynamic node or if the inputs are high before the clock sets low then the voltage at node N_2 is not sufficient to turn MP_4 completely to OFF state (MP_4 is operating near its cut off region). The resistance of MP_4 will be lesser than in OFF resistance allowing the dynamic node to get charge high. The charging of the dynamic node is called precharging phase. In this case output of the domino circuit is independent of the inputs applied at the evaluation network only the leakage current is dependent on the input vectors applied, the combination of clock and inputs low clock and low input (CLIL) and low clock and high input (CLIH) is shown in Fig.5 and Fig.6 respectively.

Figure 5. A two-input Lector Dual- V_t domino AND gate in CLIL state. The most significant components of subthreshold and gate oxide leakage currents are illustrated with arrows. High- V_t transistors are represented by thick line in channel region.

Figure 6. A k-input Lector Dual- V_t domino OR gate in CLIH state. The most significant components of subthreshold and gate oxide leakage currents are illustrated with arrows. High- V_t transistors are represented by thick line in channel region.

Now when the clock turns high or standby mode this is called evaluation phase, depending on the inputs the dynamic node gets charged or discharged. If all the inputs are low the dynamic node will not be discharged by the evaluation network and the output of the inverter will be low and it turn ON the transistor MP_2 (high- V_t), the voltage at node N_1 will turn ON the transistor MN_1 (high- V_t) but the voltage induced at node N_2 will not cut off the transistor MP_4 it will operate near cut-off region offering high resistance path between V_{DD} and ground reducing sub threshold and gate leakage current. In this CHIL sleep state as shown in Fig. 7 all the transistors in evaluation network exhibits both the I_{sub} and I_{gate} leakage current simultaneously. In this case I_{sub} dominates

I_{gate} therefore CHIL is not a leakage reduction sleep state for the proposed circuits. For other sleep state CHIH as shown in Fig. 8 the dynamic node will be discharged through the evaluation network and the output of the inverter will be high. Transistor MP_2 will turn OFF, the voltage at node N_1 will operate the transistor MN_2 near its cut off region again offering high resistance path. The potential at node N_2 will turn ON the transistor MP_4 . So by introducing the low- V_t LCTs the resistance between V_{DD} and ground is increased and simultaneously propagation delay of the domino circuit is also increased. The propagation delay will be controlled by sizing of the LCTs. Lector stacking retains the logic state during standby mode as in the standard dual- V_t domino logic. In CHIH only I_{gate} flows through the evaluation transistors and therefore this is the leakage reduction state in standby mode.

Figure 7. A k-input Lector Dual- V_t domino OR gate in CHIL state. The most significant components of subthreshold and gate oxide leakage currents are illustrated with arrows. High- V_t transistors are represented by thick line in channel region.

Figure 8. A k-input Lector Dual- V_t domino OR gate in CHIH state. The most significant components of subthreshold and gate oxide leakage currents are illustrated with arrows. High- V_t transistors are represented by thick line in channel region.

4. SIMULATION RESULTS

BISM4 device model [18] is used for simulating the standard dual- V_t domino logic and proposed technique circuits for accurate estimation of subthreshold and gate oxide leakage currents. Following currents are simulated in a 65nm CMOS technology ($V_{inlow}=|V_{iptlow}|=0.22V$, $V_{inhigh}=0.423V$, $|V_{tphigh}|=0.365V$, $V_{DD}=1V$ and output capacitance $C_{out}=1fF$) 2-input domino AND gate (AND2), 2-input, 4-input and 8-input domino OR gates (OR2, OR4 and OR8 respectively) by the HSPICE tool [19-20]. All these circuits are designed with standard dual- V_t domino and proposed dual- V_t technique. To have a reasonable comparison the sizing of NMOS and PMOS are equal in both the technique circuits. For measuring active power consumption clock pulse of 30ns is applied and measured for low and high inputs at low and high die temperatures. Comparison is done for total leakage power consumption in all the circuits by both the techniques during ideal and non ideal mode for low and high inputs at 25°C and 110°C. The low and high input states covers all the worst-case scenario for leakage power consumption that fall in the intermediate state of inputs because the maximum number of OFF transistor will occur when all the inputs are low and minimum number of OFF transistor will occur when all the inputs are high.

4.1. Active Power Consumption

Active Power Consumption of the domino circuits are shown in Fig.9 at 25°C and 110°C. The result shows that active power in lector dual- V_t circuits is reduced as compared with the standard dual- V_t domino circuits. At 25°C the active power consumption decreases by 39.6% in AND2 , 41.3% in OR2, 49.7% in OR4, 57.9% in OR8 and at 110°C 36.2% in AND2, 32.4% in OR2, 40.3% in OR4, 38.5% in OR8 when compared with standard dual- V_t domino circuits. It is observed that lector dual- V_t technique produces slightly weak logic levels due to which it leads to the reduction of active power consumption. Similarly, it is applicable for other domino circuits.

Figure 9. Active power consumption of two domino circuit techniques at 25°C and 110°C. For each circuit power consumption is normalized to the power consumed by standard dual- V_t domino technique.

4.2. Leakage Power Consumption at 25⁰C

In this part, it is assumed that sleep period is long and the sleep temperature has fallen to the room temperature. At low temperature in sub-65nm technology I_{gate} is dominant over I_{sub} , based on simulation result for the proposed domino circuit as shown in Table 2, CHIL and CLIH states are preferred for reduction of leakage current.

Table 2. Leakage power saving at 25⁰C compared with standard dual- V_t domino circuits

	AND2	OR2	OR4	OR8
CHIL	83.79%	43.86%	46.25%	50.52%
CLIH	69.7%	69.3%	73.2%	92.68%

The proposed dual V_t domino technique reduces the total leakage power by 43.86% to 83.79% for CHIL state and 69.3% to 92.68% for CLIH as compared with standard dual V_t domino circuits. Based on result analysis, CLIH state is most suitable for wide OR domino circuits at room temperature for low leakage power consumption but for AND gate best results obtained at CHIL state.

4.3. Leakage Power Consumption at 110⁰C

In this part, it is assumed that the sleep mode is short and the temperature keeps 110⁰C during the short sleep period. At high temperature, I_{sub} is dominant over I_{gate} , based on simulation result for the proposed domino circuits as shown in Table 3, same as at 25⁰C, CHIL and CLIH states are preferred for reduction of leakage current.

Table 3. Leakage power saving at 110⁰C compared with standard dual- V_t domino circuits

	AND2	OR2	OR4	OR8
CHIL	66.7%	11.42%	18.1%	24.5%
CLIH	50.83%	57.4%	65.68%	72.73%

The proposed dual- V_t domino techniques reduces the leakage power by 18.1% to 66.7% for CHIL state and 50.83% to 72.73% for CLIH state as compared to standard dual V_t domino circuits. Based on simulation results, same as at 25⁰C, CLIH state is suitable for wide fan-in domino circuits but for AND gate CHIL state shows the low leakage power consumption at high temperature.

5. CONCLUSION

In the sub-65nm technologies both the gate dielectric and subthreshold leakage currents must be suppressed for reducing power consumption. Therefore, a new domino technique is proposed for simultaneously reducing gate oxide and subthreshold leakage currents in domino logic circuits at different temperatures.

The proposed domino circuit technique exploits the level stacking effect employed between precharge and evaluation network and characteristics of high- V_t NMOS transistors used as input transistors of domino circuits. Result shows reduction of active power by 39.6% to 57.9% at low and 32.4% to 40.3% at high die temperatures. At low and high temperature CLIH state is preferred for wide OR gates, proposed work improves the leakage power by 69.3% to 92.68% at low temperature and at high temperature the improvement in total leakage power by 58.83% to 72.73% when compared with standard dual- V_t domino circuits. This technique can be used for very high speed low power applications.

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